

**ANALYZING THE IMPACT OF DIFFERENT TYPES OF FOOD
PRESERVATIVES ON THE GROWTH OF MOLD****Bakhtiyarova Dildora****Kokand city 11th grade pupil of****School number 9****ABSTRACT:**

Preservatives are substances, both natural and artificial, that are added to a variety of goods in order to prevent premature decomposition and to prolong their shelf life. It is common to find preservatives in a large variety of foods and cosmetics. But what some may not know is that preservatives are also added to non-conventional items such as pharmaceuticals and wood.

Keywords: preservatives, benzoate of sodium, public catering establishment, salad production.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The use of chemical preservatives is modulated by the maximum permitted levels. These amounts vary between countries. Processors should check with their local authorities for the local regulations and for the regulations in the country of sale. Chemical preservatives cannot be used to paper over poor-quality raw materials. They are only combined as a precaution to extend the shelf life of products by inhibiting microbial spoilage. Some chemical preservatives can cloud the flavor of fruit juices if the recommended level is exceeded. Some consumers prefer to deplete fruit juices with no chemical additives. They may be prepared to pay a premium for these products. Advocated additives to reduce PH. Organic acids, which are both naturally present in foods during fermentation or which are added to foods during processing, have been used for many years for food preservation. The most commonly used organic acids contain citric, succinic, malic, tartaric, benzoic, lactic, and propionic acids. Citric acid is found in citrus fruits. This acid is more effective than acetic and lactic acids at prohibiting the growth of thermophilic bacteria. Malic acid is, to a great degree, found in fruit and vegetables. It prohibits the growth of yeasts and some bacteria due to a decrease in pH. Tartaric acid is present in grapes and pineapples. Benzoic acid is the most widely used preservative. It falls out naturally in cranberries, raspberries, plums, prunes, cinnamon, and cloves. Benzoic acid is for the most part used as an antifungal agent in fruit-based and fruit beverages, fruit products, bakery products,

and margarine. Lactic acid is not, as might be expected, present in foods but is formed during the fermentation of sugar by lactic acid bacteria. Lactic acid inhibits the growth of spore-forming bacteria at pH 5.0 but does not affect the growth of yeast and molds. Propionic acid occurs in foods through natural processing. It is found in Swiss cheese at concentrations of up to 1%. It is effective against mold and bacteria. As is known, the public catering system is characterized by a variety of assortments of ready-made dishes with high calorie and nutritional properties. A feature of a person's daily diet is a balanced and well-chosen menu, including first, second, and third courses, salads, pastries, etc. Each dish from these groups is characterized by its culinary, thermal, and mechanical processing. Dishes prepared from raw or boiled vegetables, seasoned with vegetable oil, mayonnaise, or sour cream, have special requirements for storage conditions, distribution, and microbiological safety. The greatest interest was generated by studying the influence of different concentrations of preservatives on the shelf life of cold dishes and their safety in the sale of this type of product. A widely used food additive in public catering is benzo-sodium (E211) of various concentrations, allowing to increase the shelf life of multi-hy cold dishes when selling them. Sodium benzoate [C₆H₅COONa] is the sodium salt benzoic acid, white powder, odorless, and an approved preservative volume in Russia and European countries [1]. The purpose of the work was to study the effect of different concentrations of benzoate on trium when added to raw vegetable salads, as well as the effect of the preservative on the microbotic contamination of the product. The first stage of the work was the study of microbiological indicators. We selected salads suitable for research. Salads were prepared in accordance with GOST R 50763-95. "General natural nutrition Culinary products are sold to the public. General technical conditions, Viya" This standard establishes general technical requirements for culinary production products sold to the population, acceptance rules, and control methods ensuring their safety for human life, health, and the environment. The provisions of this standard apply to culinary products produced by public enterprises (270 food supply) of various forms of ownership as well as citizen-entrepreneurs. To assess microbiological indicators of the quality of culinary products, we use standardized methods of analysis provided for in the sanitary, hygienic, and sanitary-anti-epidemiological rules and norms, methodological local instructions, and recommendations of the State Committee for Sanitary and Epidemiological Supervision. Sampling and preparation: they are analyzed for microbiological studies in accordance with GOST 9225, GOST 26668, and GOST 26669.

1.2 DIFFERENT FOOD PRESERVATIVES

In all products, except fermented milk [2], decreasing the number of mesophilic aerobic and facultative anaerobic microorganisms, coliform bacteria (coliforms), coagulase-positive staphylococci, identification of pathogenic microorganisms, including salmonella and bacteria of the genus protea, is carried out in accordance with methodological instructions, as well as GOST 9225, GOST 9958, GOST R 50480, and GOST 26972; microbiological standards, according to MBT 5061 or in accordance with regulatory documentation for products; hygienic indicators, quality and safety, according to methods approved by health authorities; When developing a specific recipe for adding a preservative to the product, we took into account We have the following indicators: 1. The acidity of the environment, which affects the effectiveness of preservatives—the more acidic The higher the environment in which the product is, the less preservative is required to be added to it. 2. Calorie content of foods: low-calorie foods have high water content and are easily spoiled, so the amount of preservative added to them should be 30–40% more than recommended for regular products. 3. The content of sugar and/or other substances, the addition of which exhibits conditioning properties and reduces the required amount of preservative.

1.3 NATAMYCIN

Natamycin is an earthy antimicrobial peptide produced by the strain *Streptomyces natalensis*. It effectively acts as an antifungal preservative on different food products like yogurt, khoa, sausages, juices, wines, etc. In addition, it has been used as a biopreservative and is generally recognized as a dependable ingredient for various food applications. In this research paper, natamycin properties, production methods, toxicity, and application as a natural preservative in different foods are emphasized. This research paper also focuses on the optimal conditions and processes required for natamycin production. The mode of action and inhibitory effect of natamycin on yeast, mold inhibition, its formulation, and dosage to carry on various food products, coatings, and hurdle applications are resumed. Understanding the scientific factors in natamycin's production process, its toxicity, and its efficiency as a preservative will open the door to its practical application in various food products. Natamycin is a white or creamy-white powder with a molecular weight of 665.75 g/mol. The empirical formula is C₃₃H₄₇N₁₃O₁₃ with an isoelectric pH of 6.5 (Brik, 1981). Natamycin shows poor solubility in water (~40 µg/mL), but it is soluble in organic solvents (Davidson and Doan, 2020). The stability of natamycin depends on various factors like the solvent used, temperature, pressure, pH, light (UV and fluorescent light), temperature, oxidants, heavy metals, etc. Due to its low

solubility in water, natamycin remains on the surface of the food products (specifically used for the surface treatment of cheese) instead of migrating inside the food and thereby maintaining its preservative effect optimally. Natamycin showed a high solubility in a 75% aqueous solution of methanol at a pH of 2.0, a temperature of 30 °C, and a pressure of 1 atm (Zeng et al., 2013). Luo et al. (2008) reported that temperature directly increases natamycin's solubility in isopropanol and methanol. Its solubility in an aqueous solution and its stability can be effectively enhanced by the encapsulation of natamycin in a methyl- β -cyclodextrin complex without compromising its antifungal potential.

2. THE IMPACTS OF FOOD PRESERVATIVES

Actually, what are preservatives, and should we all avoid them?

Indeed, preservatives are substances, both natural and artificial, that are appended to a variety of goods in order to prevent premature decomposition and prolong their shelf life. It is common to find preservatives in a large variety of foods and cosmetics. However, what some may not recognize is that preservatives are also added to non-conventional items such as pharmaceuticals and wood. There are different types of preservatives. There are two types of preservatives: natural and artificial/chemical. Both of them aim to preserve the life of an item, though they can differ in many ways. However, both use the same antimicrobial preservation methods.

Antioxidants: slow down or fully stop the oxidation process. Enzymes: Halt the expiration of cosmetics and products. Natural preservatives are, for the most part, used in foods and beverages to help reduce rotting and preserve the item's color and flavor. However, they are also found in cosmetics and other hygiene products. Common examples of natural preservatives include aloe vera, citric acid, lemon juice, rosemary extract, **sodium, sorbic** acid, and sugar.

The product should be tested for compliance with microbiological safety in accordance with SanPiN 2.3.2.1078-01. Salads produced at enterprise catering establishments suggest increasing the shelf life from 12 hours to 5 days by adding preservatives [3, 4]. Salads made from raw vegetables with mayonnaise dressing were selected for the study. During the experiment, sodium benzoate [C₆H₅COONa] was used in concentrations of 0.15% and 0.25%. Traditionally, sodium benzoate is available in three commercial forms: powder, flakes, and granules [4]. The action of this preservative is aimed at suppressing the life-inactivity of yeasts

and molds. Bacteria are only partially inhibited; therefore, the effect of the preservative on bacterial microflora was studied. In accordance with this, the following was prepared for the experiment: Control option (K): salad without preservative; Experiment 1 (O1): preservative concentration 0.15%; Experiment 2 (O2): preservative concentration 0.25%. The studies were carried out in dynamics [5–10], i.e., lettuce samples were taken at the beginning of the nom stage (0 point), after 12 hours, 24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, and 120 hours. The results of the study are presented in Table 2. According to the results of the study at the initial stage (point 0), salads completely met the requirements of SanPiN (Table 1). Microbiological indicators were: KMAFAnM: $1 \cdot 10^4$ CFU/g; yeast: 120 CFU/g. After taking a control sample, the salads were divided into three parts: K, O1, and O2. In the experimental versions, a preservative was added.

271 Table 1: Microbiological indicators for salads made from raw vegetables and fruits weight of the product (g), which is not allowed KMAFAnM, CFU/g, no more than coliform E. coli S. aureus Proteus Pathogenic salmonella Yeast, CFU/g, no more mold, CFU/g, no more $5 \cdot 10^4$ 0.1 1.0 1.0- 25 200 50 KMAFAnM: number of mesophilic aerobic and facultative anaerobic microorganisms [CFU/g] [5]; Coliform bacteria: coliform bacteria E. coli- Escherichia coli, a group conditionally distinguished by morphological and cultural characteristics of bacteria of the enterobacteria family, used by sanitary microbiology as a marker of fecal contamination, belongs to the group of sanitary-indicative microorganisms; S. aureus-Staphylococcus aureus is the causative agent of many infections and diseases, and it may be at the top of the list of bacteria that cause food poisoning.

Proteus: straight motile rods, facultative anaerobes, diarrhea, infections, urinary tract lesions; Pathogenic Salmonella refers to pathogenic types of microorganisms that form personal antigens in food. Yeasts: some species of yeasts are facultative and opportunistic pathogens that cause food spoilage and illness in people with weakened immune systems; Molds are fungi that produce mycotoxins with inhibitory or toxic effects, causing the spoilage of food products. Adding a preservative to the salad recipe during the study period had varied personal concentrations and different effects on microbiological parameters. 272 So, after 12 hours, the prototypes, according to the QMAFAnM indicator, are characterized by a decrease relative to control: K = $4.5 \cdot 10^4$ CFU/g; O = $5.5 \cdot 10^3$ CFU/g; and O = $2.5 \cdot 10^3$ CFU/g. Also, there was marked inhibition of the amount of yeast per 1 g of the product under study: K = 250 CFU/g; O = 100 CFU/g; and O = 50 CFU/g. Molds are observed only in the control (50 CFU/g). After 24 hours, a similar trend is observed, with a clear inhibitory effect in a prototype with a preservative concentration of 0.15%. Show- The value of QMAFAnM in the control sample (K) was $6.5 \cdot 10^4$

CFU/g; in O1 it was $3.2 \cdot 10^3$ CFU/g; in O2 it was $4.5 \cdot 10^3$ CFU/g. Undoubtedly, this is due to the effective action of benzoate sodium on a specific group of microorganisms in small doses. According to the results of the study, it is clear that the control option (K) after 24 hours does not comply with SanPiN, so the indicators of KMAFAnM and yeast are higher than the normative ones (Fig. 1). After 48 hours, the prototypes (O1 and O2) comply with sanitary regulations. In the control variant, there is a further increase in the QMAFAnM indicator ($7.6 \cdot 10^4$ CFU/g). There is a slight decrease in the number of yeasts (120 CFU/g). After 72 hours, all microbiological indicators in the test samples also comply with SanPiN (Table 2). The KMAFAnM indicator was in O1— $1.1 \cdot 10^2$ CFU/g; in O2— $3 \cdot 10^3$ CFU/g. The effectiveness of sodium benzoate at a lower dose has been noted. After 120 hours, the QMAFAnM indicator decreases both in the control and in the experimental samples (K = $5 \cdot 10^4$ CFU/g; O1 = $1.5 \cdot 10^2$ CFU/g; O2 = $3.1 \cdot 10^3$ CFU/g). This is probably due to the influence of low temperatures on the vital activity of microorganisms.

3. CONCLUSION:

In experienced options, there is a further decrease in the total number of microorganisms. Plies: neither are observed only in the control variant (K): 150 CFU/g. 273 Thus, based on the data obtained, we can conclude that the experience samples with sodium benzoate concentrations of 0.15% and 0.25% have a positive influence on microbiological parameters for 120 hours. Thus, based on the data obtained, we can conclude that the experience samples with sodium benzoate concentrations of 0.15% and 0.25% have a positive influence on microbiological parameters for 120 hours. A product with a preservative substance meets the requirements of SanPiN for micro-biological indicators. At the second stage of the work, microbiological safety studies were carried out on product safety according to organoleptic assessment indicators of control and experimental samples.

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